

DEMOCRACY AND NATIONAL INTEGRATION: PERSPECTIVES FROM ELECTIONS AND ELECTIONEERING IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The discourse to build a nation out of Nigeria has been very old and continues. There is no gain saying that a united and integrated Nigerian state is a veritable instrument for nation-building. This paper is on democracy and national integration. It is aimed at examining the reasons behind the problems of national integration. In the analysis, the theoretical framework applied is the Integration Theory. We also utilized content analysis. The paper notes that there are many factors that lead to national disintegration, but the focus of the paper is on election and electioneering in Nigeria. Elections in Nigeria are known to be replete with violence, destruction of lives and property, rigging and hate speech. As these unwholesome activities and attitude go on, they develop centrifugal factors that set the ethnic nationalities apart. In the face of these, the paper contends that it would be a herculean task to build a nation out of over two hundred and fifty ethnic nationalities. It recommends that one of the major steps to building Nigeria for development and unity is by getting our electoral process right, free and fair and all inclusive for all ethnic groups. The paper also recommends that fines should be imposed on defaulters.*

INTRODUCTION

Democracy is known to be a global tool for development, unity, stability and representation. Democracy is acknowledged to be the most viable system of government to achieve or be vehicle for development. Even countries which hitherto adopted other system of government

such as Russia or former Soviet Union, have now individually and or in group abandoned the socialist approach for liberal democracy. Also in Africa, countries are widening their democratic space to include other shades of opinion, for instance in Sudan and recently in Algeria. The benefits of democracy are numerous. One main

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advantage is that it has the tendency to integrate a multi-ethnic country particularly if it is properly practised with all the major tenets of democracy.

National integration has been defined in many ways, due to its multifarious usages. Coleman and Roseburg cited in Ikyase and Egberi (2014) defined National Integration as a broad process whose two dimensions are political integration and territorial integration. Political integration is progressive bridging of elite – mass gap, while territorial integration refers to the progressive reduction of cultural and regional tension in the process of creating a homogenous territorial political community. Also Olawale and Adisa (2008) define national integration as the attempt at uniting or bringing together the hitherto multi-ethnic groups with diverse cultural, historical, language, and belief system into one which would remove primordial and ethnic sentiments and loyalty.

National integration is Nigeria main challenge and since independence, Nigeria has carried out and adopted different strategies to resolve this challenge such steps include:

- i. The national youth service corps
- ii. Nigerialisation policy
- iii. Unity school system
- iv. National language policy
- v. Uniformity of local government system
- vi. National festival of Arts and Culture
- vii. National sports festival

viii. Natural football league (Edosa 2014). The policy of federal character was also to ensure that public appointments and positions were spread across zones, states, local government, wards and communities such that all ethnic, linguistic and cultural groups were represented in government institutions and agencies as much as possible (Yakubu, 2003).

Inspite of these mechanisms put in place, Nigeria still remains largely ununited, disintegrated, ethnically and religiously biased at the detriment of the overall welfare of the people and nation-building. Against this backdrop, this paper dwells on role of democracy in National integration special attention is devoted to elections and electioneering in Nigeria.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In this study, we applied integration theory in analyzing the work. Integration theory was formulated by Amitai Ezioni in 1965. He applied the model with the use of differentiation, a concept he said enables the society to be in general changes as a result of integration. According to him integration as the adoptive response of plural and medium size states to global challenges they could not face individually (Ikyase and Egberi 2014). Etzioni noted that integration presupposes existence of elements of pluralism such as ethnic, socio-cultural, language or political. Integration creates territories unit that reduces tension in a democratic society in order to bring out unity

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and homogeneity, reduction in political inequality and ethnic groups.

This theory is important in explaining democracy and national integration. This is because fear of political domination has contributed to the lack of national consensus and integration. According to Ikyase and Egberi (2014), the Nigerian democracy is characterized by a great deal of anti-democratic practices, for instance elections are rigged in very shameful manner, vote buying is rampant, violence and killings at election are common. The problems of ethnicity, regionalism etc continues to foster disunity and distergration. It is only this basis, that this theory addresses the issues raised in the paper.

Conceptual Clarifications

(i) Democracy

The search for a generic definition of democracy is fraught with conceptual and epistemological problem (Ebohon and Emuedo, 2009) its most popular conception of democracy is government by the people for the people. Riker (1965) conceives democracy as being a form of government in which the rulers are fully responsible to the ruled in order to realize self-respect for everybody. Schnitter (2003) quoted in Ebohon and Enuedo (2009), opined that Rikers definition failed to capture the generic quality of democracy, which is not democracy is a system of government in which rulers are held accountable for their action in the public domain by citizens.

In the words of Anifowose (2005) cited in Ikyase and Ejuo (2014) democracy is essentially a method of organizing society politically, with five basic elements without which no community can call itself truly democratic. These are equality sovereignty of the people, respect for the human life, rule of law and liberty of individuals. The definition undermines the cardinal demerits of democracy which is the prominent role of political parties. It is this deficiency that Haruna (2010) remedied when he defined democracy and said it entailed meaningful and extensive competition among individuals and organized groups directly or indirectly for the major position of governmental power.

The concept of democracy can also be regarded as governmental system that involves the widest spectrum of participation, either through election or through administration of accepted policies. It is a government founded on the principle of rule of law which is against arbitrariness, highhandedness, dictatorship and anti-ethical to military regime (Dauda and Avidime, 2007) cited in Oyediran and Adeshola, 2017).

Further adumbrating on democracy Lumumba-Kasongo making reference to Julius Nyerere, said that democracy means much more than voting on the basis of adult suffrage every few years, it means among other an attitude of tolerance and willingness to operate with others on terms of equality. An essential ingredient of

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democracy is that it is based on the quality of all the people within a nation's boundary.

The democratic process is the machinery that produces elected officials and general rules that should govern the people. However, according to Dahl (1989) no democratic process is perfect but every democratic culture has the capacity for correcting their own failures.

National Integration

National integration can be referred to as nation-building, national unity, national cohesion, nationality and oneness (Oyediran and Adeshola 2017), Duverger (1976) conceptualized national integration as a process of unifying a society which tends to make it a harmonious city, based on an order its members regard as equitably harmonious. Morrison (et al, 1972) have also conceived national integration as a process by which members of a social system develop linkages, so that boundaries of the system persists overtime and boundaries of sub-system become less consequential in affecting behavior. In this process, members of the social system develop an escalating sequence of contact, cooperation, consensus and community.

Generally, we can say national integration entails the building of nation-state out of numerous socio-economic, religious, ethnic and geographical elements which translate from diffuse and unorganized sentiment of nationalism into the spirit of citizenship through the creation of policy and programme that are in

line with the yearnings and aspirations of the citizenry.

Election

Election is the formal process of selecting a person for public or of accepting or rejecting a political proposition by voting (www.britannica.com).

Elections were used in ancient Athens, Rome and in selection of popes etc. The origin of election in contemporary world lies in the gradual emergence of representative government in Europe and North America beginning in the 17th Century.

Elections make a fundamental contribution to democratic governance. Elections enable voters to select leaders and to hold them accountable for their performance in office. Accountability can be undermined when elected leaders do not care whether they are reelected or not. Elections provide political education for citizens, and ensure the responsiveness of democratic government to the will of the people. Elections serve to legitimize the acts of those who wield power. Elections reinforce stability and legitimacy of the political community, elections link citizens to each other and thereby confirm the viability of the polity and as a result elections help to facilitate social and political integration. Voting gives people an opportunity to have their say and through expressing partisanship, satisfy their need to feel a sense of belonging

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(<http://www.britannica.com/topic/election-political>).

Whether held under authoritarian or democratic regimes, elections have a ritualistic aspect. Elections and campaigns preceding them are dramatic events that are accompanied by rallies, banners, posters, headlines and television coverage all to draw the attention.

Electioneering

Electioneering is the activity that politicians and their supporters carry out in order to persuade people to vote for them or their political party in an election (Collins Dictionary.com visited in 1/2/20). It is also known as “to work for the success of a particular candidate or party in an election.”

Electioneering is the act of campaigning to influence the result of an election in favour of a particular candidate. The key elements of electioneering are in order to persuade them vote for the candidate or party endorsed. Examples of electioneering include campaign rallies, debates between prospective candidates for offices (Election Glossary, Polyas.com visited in 1/2/20) Ezegwu, Enemy and Ndife (2017) define political campaign/electioneering as an organized effort which is to influence the decision making process within a specific group or people. Chile (2011) cited in Efika, Nyong, Agbor and Opusunji (2019) stated that campaign refers to a systematic effort in coordinating all relevant activities over a period of time to obtain a specific

and all-encompassing objective. Aduradola and Ojukwu (2013) define it as mobilization of forces by an organization or individual to influence others in order to achieve desired political change. It shows people and political candidates’ ability to sensitize the political community in relation to making the community see them as potential and better representative of the people. Nwamuo, Asemah and Edegoh (2004) see political campaign as an organized effort which seek to influence the decision making process within a specific group. Campaign messages often contain the issues the candidate intends to share with electorates. Such message centre on policy issues and summarizes the main ideas of the campaign and they are often repeated to create lasting impression. On its own party, Ginsberg (2009) cited in Olujide, Adeyemi and Gabdeyan (2011) define political campaign as organized effort by a political party or candidate to attract the support of voters in an election. Ejika, Nyong, Agbor and Opusunju (2019) writing on forms of political campaign by electioneering candidates in Nigeria, defined it as the process whereby electorates are invested with campaign messages about prospective candidates who are dying for political position or offices. It is a planned and consistent effort made by party member to canvas for candidates of their choice. They noted there are many forms of political campaign in Nigeria, such as (i) Radio and TV campaign, (ii) Social media political

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campaign, (iii) bill board campaign, (iv) Posters and pamphlets campaign and (v) Rally campaign.

Finally, electioneering campaign has been defined by Uzonwanne, Ezenekwe and Iregbu (2016) as a process provided by law which enables a candidate to ascertain an elective office and to sensitize the populace on his party manifesto.

Elections and the challenge of National Integration

Since Nigeria gained independence in 1960, the challenge of National Integration became one of the onerous tasks faced by the country. This challenge was most glaring in the spheres of elections. The crises that erupt during election make it difficult for any rational being to believe that the country was truly prepared for democracy. For instance, the 1965 elections in western region was marred by crises and violence so much so that the west was tagged “wild, wild, west”. The civil society registered its dissatisfaction with the federal election in 1965 by refusing to pay taxes (Ifenanacho; <http://www.liste.org/journals/>). The violence and revolts which ensued, spread from the urban to the Rural and according to Ifenanacho, the anarchy completely eroded the legitimacy of the state and gave impetus to the five majors who led the first military coup in Nigeria in 1966. The collapse of the first republic demonstrated clearly the inability of the Nigerian state to

integrate the country. As Nwokeke and Jayan (2011) ascertained, the 1965 western election revealed that electoral officers colluded with political party that was favoured by the federal government to disallow voters from the opposition political party from filling their allocated nomination papers. The nature of the election rigging as summarized by Dudley (1981), Anifowose (1982); Post and Vicker (1973) indicated that Akintola and his party (NNDP), with federal government’s support, carried a staggering horrific rigging machinery, thuggery obstruction and punitive control to give NNDP an overwhelming victory. The Rulling party (Northern people, Congress NPC) supported Akintola via massive rigging and voted Chief Obafemi Awolowo’s Action Group (AG) out. Dudley (1982) cited by Nwaokeke and Juyan (2011) noted that Deputy Leader of NNDP who also was Deputy Premier of the west had said before election that whether the electorate voted for the NNDP or not, NNDP would win the elections. Ademoyega (1981) noted that in many cases AG candidates who held certificates of return that they were duly elected in their constituencies later heard their names mentioned as defeated candidates through governmental news media.

Nwokeke and Jayum noted what happened in Ondo State between Chief Akin Omoboriowo (National party of Nigeria) and Chief Michael Ajasin (Unity Party of Nigeria). Omoboriwo was

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declared winner by Electoral Commission (Fedeco) with 1,228,891 votes as against 1,015,385 votes credited to the later (Ajasin). However, based on the verdict from the electoral court, the federal court of Appeal and the Supreme Court, the result was up turned and Chief Michael Ajasin was declared winner. Evidence showed that Chief Omoboriowo scored 547,942 votes. The 1983 elections was characterized as one of the most corrupt election ever conducted in Nigeria.

In 1993, the General Babangida administration introduced the two-party system of SDP and NRC. Good as that arrangement was the whole well intentioned effort was destroyed when Gen. Bababagida annulled the General election that produced an acclaimed winner – Moshod Abiola, so as to assuage the interest of the Northern oligarchy and political machine of the North; that election was adjudged as most free and fair in the history of election in Nigeria.

This unfortunate development engendered hatred, violence and political instability, making it further difficult to consolidate, stabilize and socio-culturally integrate the country. As Nwokeke and Jayan (2011) rightly put it; the annulment of the election results threatened the political stability and unity of Nigeria and pushed the country back to deep-seated political turmoil and further military dictatorship.

Since 1999 Nigeria returned to democracy there has always been political crisis every election year. This crisis range from marginalization of groups, manipulation of votes and sometimes imposition of candidates. All these have impacted negatively of Nigeria' democracy and the process of national integration (Ikyanse and Egberi, 2014).

Egberi and Ikyanse also noted that in 2011, at the end of the Presidential election where Goodluck Jonathan was declared winner, the Muhammdu Buhari, CPC supporters interpreted the victory to be an outcome of rigging. Consequently, tension was built-up and degenerated into violent explosion mainly in the Northern states of Katsina, Kano, Kaduna, Bauchi, Adamawa, Gombe and Taraba. Protestors burnt places of religious worship, public buildings, houses of political leaders of PDP and religious leaders considered to be related to parties. They also destroyed INEC buildings and its personnel including NYSC members serving as INEC ad-hoc staff and in Bauchi State including corp members were killed. (The Nation 21 April, 2011).

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Table 1: Instances of Political Conflict, Violence, and Crisis

S/N	Date	Location	Principal Actors	Source
1	February 2003	Obudu, Cross River State	Inter-party conflict between ANPP and PDP over colonial election	Vanguard Feb. 5, 2003
2	February 2003	Jato-Aka, Benue State	Politically motivated conflict between supporters of ANPP, UNPP and PDP	Vanguard Feb. 29, 2003
3	May 12, 2003	Efurum, Delta State	Political crises between PDP and AD supporters	Vanguard, 15 May, 2003
4	February 17, 2004	Takum, Taraba State	Politically motivated mayhem between PDP and NDP over LG election	Vanguard Feb. 19, 2004
5	April 2011	Bauchi State	Politically motivated crises by CPC over alleged manipulation of votes in favour of PDP.	Nation, 23 April, 2011
6	May 10, 2011	Akwa Ibom State	Political motivated crises between PDP and CPC	Daily Trust, May 11 2011

Source: Ikyase and Egbari 2014

The beauty of democracy is that it allows for free and fair elections whereby electorate are given the opportunity to vote candidates of their choice and their votes counts. The build-up to election being devoid of rancor with political primaries being fair to all aspirants.

From the table 1 above, elections in Nigeria over the years were not free and fair and replete with imposition of candidates.

Hate speech is any speech, gesture, conduct, inviting or display which could incite people to violence. Hate speech rob others of their dignity

(Ezeibe, 2018). According to Netsser (1994), hate speech refers to all communications (whether verbal, written, symbolic) that insults a racial, ethnic and political group, whether by suggesting that they are inferior in some respect or by indicating that they are despised or not welcome for any other reason”.

According to Ezeibe (2018), the phenomenon has taken an extensive dimension in Africa and in Nigeria it has become an aspect of electioneering campaign. Political leaders in Nigeria use hate speech to divide and rule the

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people already divided along ethnic and religious lines.

Table 2: Hate speeches in Nigeria, 2010-2015

S/N	Year	Hate speaker	Hate speech	Sources
1	2010	Shehu Sani, a Kaduna based civil rights activist	President Goodluck Jonathan should not contemplate contesting the 2011 presidential election. Any attempt by him to contest amounts to incitement and a recipe for political instability	www.nigerianbestforum.com/shehu-sani-warns-jonathan-against-contesting
2	2010	National Coordinator of the Coalition of Northern Politicians, Dr. Junaidu Mohammed	It must be a Northerner or no Nigeria... If Goodluck Jonathan wins the PDP's endorsement to contest the 2011 presidential election, there would be violence.	Interview with Guardian Newspaper, 2nd November, 2010
3	2011	Presidential Candidate of Congress for Progressive Change, General Muhammadu Buhari	God willing, by 2015, something will happen. They either conduct a free and fair election or they go a very disgraceful way. If what happened in 2011 should again happen in 2015, by the grace of God, the dog and the baboon would all be soaked in blood	Reported by Lika Binniyat in Vanguard Newspaper on May 15th, 2012
4	2013	Abu King Shuluwa	Nigeria will disintegrate if Jonathan contests in 2015	Daily Independent Friday, March 8th , 2013
5	2013	Former Chairman of PDP, Colonel Ahmadu Ali (rtd)	The Yorubas are ungrateful kind of people, who do not appreciate what others have done for them	Sun Newspaper, March 16, 2013
6	2014	Publicity Secretary of All Progressive	If the 2015 elections are rigged, the party will not recognize the outcome	Leadership 21st November, 2014; Sahara Reporters

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		Congress, Alhaji Lai Mohammed	and will go ahead and form a parallel government	22nd November, 2014
7	2014	An Islamic cleric, Ima Sadiq	Muslims, vote for Buhari. It is a sin to support a non-Muslim	Twitter handle, Saturday, 27th December, 2014
8	2014	Northern Elder Forum	Those who vote for Jonathan and the PDP in 2015 will be considered an enemy of the north	<i>Vanguard</i> , 15 October 2014.
9	2013	Femi Fani-Kayode, a former Aviation Minister	The Igbos are collectively unlettered, uncouth, uncultured, unrestrained and crude in all their ways...Money and the acquisition of wealth is their sole objective and purpose in life	Daily Post, August 8, 2013
10	2013	The leader of the Niger Delta Peoples Salvation Force (NDPSF), Alhaji Mujahid Dokubo-Asari	There will be no peace, not only in the Niger Delta, but everywhere if Goodluck Jonathan is not president by 2015, except God takes his life, which we do not pray for	Vanguard Newspapers, May 5, 2013
11	2013	Chief Arthur Eze PDP Chieftain	That short man called Ngige, we gave him power and he joined the Awolowo people; the people that killed Igbos	Premium Times, November 13, 2013
12	2014	Former Governor of Akwa Ibom State, Godswill Akpabio	Those who want to take power through the back door will die. They will die	Punch Newspaper, 17th July, 2014
13	2014	Alhaji Mujahid Dokubo-Asari	2015 is more than do-or-die. You are a man and I am a man, we are going to meet at the battlefield	News Express 3rd May, 2014
14	2014	Alhaji Mujahid Dokubo-Asari	If they contest (Northerners) they are wasting their time. He who pays the piper will dictate the tune. We own them. We are feeding them. They are	http://www.vanguardngr.com/2014/12/north-ungrateful-

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			parasites. A beggar has no choice...They are beggars and parasites	parasites-asari-dokubo).
15	2015	Wife of former President, Patience Jonathan	<i>Wetin him dey find again? Him dey drag with him pikin mate, old man wey no get brain, him brain don die pata pata-</i> What is Buhari looking for? Old man that does not know his age. Your brain is dead.	At a PDP rally in Kogi state, Reported by <i>The Express New</i> , 4 March, 2014
16		Wife of former President, Patience Jonathan	Our people do not give birth to uncountable children. Our men don't give birth to children that they dump in streets. We are not like people from that part of the country (apparently the northern Nigeria)	Presidential campaign in Calabar, The Nation, March 10, 2015
17	2015	Wife of former President, Patience Jonathan	Anybody that come and tell you changes, stone that person... What you did not do in 1985, is it now that old age has caught up with you that you want to come and change...You cannot change rather you will turn back to a baby	The Complete Works of Patience Jonathan, The Nation on Sunday, 15th March
18	2015	The Governor of Ekiti State, Peter Ayodele Fayose	Buhari would likely die in office if elected, recall that Murtala Muhammed, Sani Abacha and Umaru Yar'Adua, all former heads of state from the North West like Buhari, had died in office	January 19, 2015, ThisDay and other national dailies
19	2015	Oba Akiolu of Lagos	On Saturday, if anyone of you, I swear in the name of God, goes against my wish that Ambode will be the next governor of Lagos state, the person is going to die inside this water...For the	ThisDay Newspaper, 4th April 2015

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			Igbos and others in Lagos, they should go where the Oba of Lagos heads to...	
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Source: Ezeibe (2018)

Notable hate speech during the first republic are as follows:

1. The Igbo are too dominating, if you employ an Igbo man as a labourer, he will like to take over as foreman within a short while - Late Sardauna of Sokoto, Sir Ahmadu Bello
2. The God of Africa has created the Igbo nation to lead the children of Africa from bondage of ages – The first President of Nigeria, Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe
3. Nnamdi Azikiwe’s policy was to corrode the self-respect of the Yoruba people as a group to build up the Igbos as a master race- Chief Obafemi Awolowo (Seng, & Hunt, 1986 cited in Ezeibe, 2018).

Election gifting has also constituted a cog in Nigeria’s election and therefore making it very difficult to achieve a free and fair election. A good example of election gifting is vote-buying. According to Adekola and Olumide (2019), vote buying play dominant role in determining who wins in Nigeria’s election since the Second Republic in 1979. As Schaffer and Schedler (2005) said, vote buying is an economic exchange where candidates “buy” and citizens “sell” their votes.

Election gifting does not have place in democracy and the effect is the reason why there is much

poverty, illiteracy and unemployment. However, as Adekola and Olamide stated, the ordeal of democracy in Nigeria is not a result of a failed system alone, but that of a failed people, because the system is a construct of the people. Therefore the problems in the electoral process which ranges from stealing of ballot boxes, manipulation of electoral process, election rigging, vote buying and political assassination as opined by Diamond (1994), Alemeka (2007), Animashaun, and Adekola and Olamide (2019) are challenges which have continued to affect democratic progress of the Nigerian state and therefore very difficult in achieving national integration, due to bickering, hatred and dislike at state and national levels.

Building a united and integrated nation in an atmosphere of rancor and hatred would be a difficult position to achieve. For instance, in one of the speeches credited to General Muhammadu Buhari, a former presidential candidate of congress for Progressive change (CPC) threatened former President Goodluck Jonathan to avoid using power of incumbency to rig the 2015 election or something will happen. The threat about the dog and the baboon in blood bath could mean severe fight between APC and PDP; Northern and Southern Nigeria; Christians

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and Muslims (Ezeibe, 2018). Also the speech of Shetima Ibrahim referring members of the opposition as cockroaches was a very terrible hate speech. Similarly the study of Ezeibe showed that hate speech credited to the former First Lady Patience Jonathan made election in Okrika in Rivers State violent with gunmen attacking campaign grounds of APC, causing disruption of APC rally with the explosions and sporadic gun fire on the 17th February, 2015.

Sule, Sambo, Adamu (2020), captured the campaign process for 2019 election appropriately when they noted that violence, insecurity, political banditry, intimidation, hate speeches and campaign of calumny were deployed. Politicians became abusive and insulting in their pronouncement. They incited their supporters to exhibit and unleash violence against their opponents, Religious sentiments was exploited to manipulate followers and ethnic politics played prominent role in politicians' aspiration for power.

Sule, Sambo, Adamu (2020) wrote that during 2019 election, religion clerics were used to support corrupt politicians who bribed them. During the presidential election, in 2019, two major contenders were Muslims and Fulanis and both came from the North but the religious clerics decided to support the APC candidate overwhelmingly identified him as moral, incorruptible and pious, while they portrayed the PDP candidate as corrupt and irreligious. A large

atmosphere of hate and rancor pervaded the political environment and this makes it difficult to build one and united nation-state.

Elections in Nigeria are characterized with violence and thuggery at vitually all levels. The 2019 election was not an exception. Due to violence, election in the following states of Rivers, Kano, Sokoto, Pateau, Benue, Bauchi and Adamawa were declared inconclusive (Sule, Sambo, Adamu, 2020). This sad development was reported by domestic and International observers and recorded on Videotape by BBC (Hausa) correspondence, particularly the Kano situation, where lethal weapons and ballot snatching was rampant.

Coupled with this, are the issues of voter apathy. Since 1999 return to civil rule, there has been downward trend in public trust support of the democratic system. This is largely due to disappointment citizens have suffered in the democratic process; failed promises, bad governance, election violence and rigging of results during elections. Infact Akinyemi (2019) wrote that former president Muhammadu Buhari was re-elected by just 18% of registered voters, while only 35% registered voters voted in the 2019 election. Such high level political apathy is a result of low public trust and does not engender national integration and oneness as there are always centrifugal forces setting the country apart.

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Conclusion

National integration is the desire of all multi-ethnic and multi-national federal state. For Nigeria, the need for national unity, cannot be over-emphasized. In the quest for unity and development, the use and deployment of democracy and democratic rules becomes paramount. Major elements of democracy that are sine qua non for national integration are elections and electioneering. As the study has shown elections in Nigeria are replete with violence, rigging, vote buying, destruction of lives and property. This study also revealed that hate speech is preponderant in electioneering campaign in Nigeria and as is known, hate speech has very long damaging effect in the unity of the country. In the face of these challenges, national integration would be difficult to attain. To alleviate these problems and put Nigeria on the path of unity and development, the paper recommends that electoral umpire in Nigeria should endeavour against all odds to conduct a free and fair election in the country. Election primaries and electioneering campaigns should be closely monitored and supervised (with fines imposed where necessary) to deter politicians and supporters who would resort to violence, hate speech, and other unwholly acts during campaigns and party rally. The paper recommends also that electoral offences tribunal be set up to handle such offences as hate speech,

vote buying, election rigging, violence during election, etc.

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